

DIGITALIZATION AND ECONOMIC GROWTH IN PAKISTAN: AN EMPIRICAL ANALYSIS OF THE SERVICES SECTOR (2010–2024)

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Abstract

The study investigates the impact of digitalization on economic growth in Pakistan's services sector from 2010 to 2024, using an empirical approach based on multiple linear regression analysis. Digitalization was measured through four key indicators: The E-Governance Development Index, Internet Access (% of people using the internet), Mobile Cellular Subscriptions, and Fixed Broadband Subscriptions, while Economic Growth served as the dependent variable. The results from the ANOVA test ($F = 2.387$, $p = 0.121$) indicate that digitalization collectively has a positive but statistically insignificant impact on economic growth. The regression results reveal that Internet Access ($B = 0.209$, $p = 0.131$), Mobile Subscriptions ($B = 0.245$, $p = 0.162$), and Fixed Broadband ($B = 0.041$, $p = 0.922$) exert positive yet insignificant effects, whereas the E-Governance Index ($B = -56.109$, $p = 0.021$) shows a significant but negative association with growth. These findings suggest that Pakistan's digital transformation is still in a transitional stage where digital infrastructure and governance reforms have not yet translated into consistent economic benefits. The study recommends strengthening e-governance implementation, expanding broadband and internet accessibility, and integrating digital policies with service-sector development to enhance the long-term contribution of digitalization to sustainable economic growth.

INTRODUCTION

Chapter#1

Background

Two primary engines of the modern world economy today are considered as economic expansion and digital transformation. The

continuous increase in a country's production, employment, and income levels, which enhances life standards, is known as economic growth. By contrast, digitalization uses mobile communication, artificial intelligence, and

contemporary technologies like the internet to speed up commercial and governmental operations, make them more effective and accessible. Emerging as one of the most potent driving forces of economic progress in our linked world of today, digitalization helps countries to be more efficient, original and competitive (World Bank, 2016).

Pakistan like other poor countries, has serious financial problems including unemployment, poverty and poor infrastructure. Such persistent issues have hampered country growth over decades. Still, the spread of digital technologies gives a chance to overcome these obstacles and provide fresh growth possibilities. Leading the way in this transformation has been the services industry covering trade, finance, education, and information technology among other fields. Online sites like Daraz.pk and Foodpanda.pk have expanded business markets and produced thousands of jobs (UNCTAD, 2019). Easypaisa and JazzCash have likewise served millions of unbanked people financial solutions, therefore promoting financial inclusion and small-scale business (GSMA, 2019; Demirgüç Kunt et al., 2018).

Pakistan's IT and Business Process Outsourcing (BPO) sectors also show the economic effects of digitalization. With significant expansion in this area, Pakistan's IT exports in 2021 exceeded USD 2.1 billion (Pakistan Software Export Board, 2021). Government measures like the National Incubation Centers (Ministry of IT & Telecommunication, 2020) are helping digital startups and innovation, therefore revealing Pakistan's interest in the world digital economy. Investment in technology and competent human resources can help developing nations to contend as major global players, as Kshetri (2010) observes.

Problem Statement

In spite of these encouraging trends, Pakistan digital evolution is still constrained by a number of institutional and structural hurdles. Major portions of the population particularly those living in rural areas, continue to be deprived of access to quality internet, digital hardware and skill sets. Inadequate infrastructure, cyber security issues and poor

policy coordination further retard momentum (Qureshi, 2014). These issues create a "digital divide" hindering fair participation in the digital economy. Without robust governance, digital infrastructure and digital literacy Pakistan stands to lose competitiveness in the region as well as in sustainable economic growth.

Significance of the Study:

This research is crucial because it examines how digitalization could drive economic expansion in Pakistan's services industry from 2010–2025. Generating employment, innovation, and worldwide commerce depends much on the services sector. Policymakers will be helped to identify practical answers for Pakistan's economic issues by their knowledge of how digitalization affects this sector. By describing the obstacles to digital adoption and presenting evidence-based policy planning ideas for the future, the study also adds value. This study helps, generally, to guide the broader discussion on how growing economies such as Pakistan can use technology to promote inclusive and sustainable expansion.

Research Questions

- How has digitalization impacted the economic growth of Pakistan's services industry between 2010–2025?
- What are the main barriers limiting Pakistan's effective digital transformation?
- What policy measures can help digitalization have a greater effect on inclusive and sustainable economic development?

1.1. Research Objectives

- To investigate the connection between Pakistan's services sector's digitalization and GDP growth.
- To find significant roadblocks limiting digital transformation.
- To offer appropriate policy ideas assisting Pakistan to use digitization for job creation and sustainable development.

Chapter# 2**Literature review:**

Increasing empirical research reveals a positive correlation between digitalization and economic growth especially when digital adoption is strong and backed by infrastructure and human capital. For Pakistan, UAAR et al. (2024) use time-series co integration (1995–2022) and demonstrate that internet and fixed broadband penetration increase real GDP per person in the Using panel ARDL on 87 emerging economies (2000–2023). Asma et al., (2024) show how mobile subscriptions mainly impact short-run growth and emphasize variations across ICT indicators. Long run, arguing for digital investment, find too that money supply, labor force participation, gross fixed capital formation (GFCF), and digital investment (DI) all favorably affect infrastructure growth. Zhang et al., (2022) show that the digital economy has a beneficial influence on the development of Belt and Road nations and advise that digitalization drivers structural upgrading and employment. These macro investigations repeatedly stress that widespread connection and digital infrastructure are fundamental prerequisites for digitalization to result in long term expansion. Though dependent on human capital, digitalization has a beneficial impact on entrepreneurship.

Iqbal et al., (2025) using fixed effects, examine 139 nations (2011–2019) and discover that digitalization and GDP increase greatly support entrepreneurship; especially, the effect is more pronounced where tertiary education (human capital) is strong; Digital skills are advanced. This confirms the importance of knowledge and abilities in transforming internet access into creative entrepreneurial activity and implies complementarities between human capital growth and digital policy. Many papers stress the growth potential of digital financial services yet also identify industry heterogeneity and possible hazards. Ahmad et al. (2020) find that human capital and digital financial inclusion (breadth, depth, degree of digital penetration) substantially support local economic growth in China. Tabassum for Pakistan, et al. (date not given in abstract) find that long run growth is positively impacted by ATMs, mobile wallets, and

internet banking; however, POS transactions might not be. look at consumption patterns instead of productive investment.

Syed et al. (2021) demonstrate that digital finance lowers the size of the shadow economy in South Asian Countries may, however, raise systemic risk, therefore policymakers must balance inclusion with financial stability. Although results differ by industry, digitalization enhances firm-level performance. Mushtaq et al Utilising RBV theory, al. (2024) find that Pakistani SMEs that invest in managerial digital literacy and digital infrastructure perform better. Liu et al. (2024) Present a two-stage empirical study of Pakistan's banking sector (2006–2020) and show that digital transformation improves banking efficiency and promotes bank convergence. Gul et al. Limited but good relationships between digitization and financial performance are mediated by servitization found in 2023. Although stressing the necessity, Manzoor et al. (2021) and Asif Javed (2020) emphasize the part the ICT sector plays in Pakistan's exports, freelancing, and job creation. for more infrastructure and skills training. Taken together, these industry research show that the advantages of digitalization depend on infrastructure, governance, and company capabilities. Many Pakistan oriented investigations find distinct barriers to digital transformation. Nadeem et al. (2024) demonstrate via ISM and Fuzzy QFD that significant impediments include poor awareness of digital possibilities, inadequate ICT infrastructure, and market limitations. As treatments for hurdles, they push for artificial intelligence, research and development, and standardization.

For Asia Pacific, Shakeel et al. (2022) stresses as important elements cost, network coverage, and human capital. Van Bon (2021) discovers complicated interactions between governance and digitalization: digitalization and governance improve growth but their interplay can be murky, therefore requiring Well designed institutional frameworks. Sheikh (2021) raises the risk side digitalization can generate fresh corruption or cyber risk vectors therefore stressing the need of strong governance and cyber security. The examined studies use a variety of approaches: time series

co integration and ECM (UAAR et al., 2024), panel ARDL (Asma et al., 2024), fixed effects Mixed methods like ISM + Fuzzy QFD (Nadeem et al., 2024), panel regressions (Iqbal et al., 2025), PLS-SEM and structural equation modeling (Shakeel et al., Gul et al.). This variety shows how research on digitalization gains from both macro econometric approaches (to identify long-run correlations) and micro/firm level surveys (to expose mechanisms). One yearly measurement helps. One benefit is that numerous digital indicators internet penetration, broadband, mobile subscriptions, digital finance proxies, installed ICT capacity are easily accessible, allowing for quantitative evaluation a point pertinent to your intended assessment. Two significant voids directly pertinent to your planned quantification are revealed in the provided abstracts, despite compelling data that digitalization encourages growth, entrepreneurship, and sectoral efficiency. Your initiative: (1) Not much investigated in the Pakistan literature shown here; most research concentrates on domestic digitalization consequences rather than on external investments as conduits of projecting productive capacity overseas; (2) Sectoral Above in the Pakistan focused digitalization literature, studies on green technologies (solar) as tools of international influence are mostly missing. Therefore, a definite specialty exists: Examining how China's outside FDI particularly in solar innovation serves as a conduit for projecting new quality productive forces globally, and whether measurable indicators (FDI flows, technology) In a Pakistani case study, transfer, installed capacity, patents, and business connections can help to measure that impact.

Chapter#3

Methodology

3.1. Introduction

This study employs a quantitative, time-series econometric approach to examine the impact of digitalization on the economic growth of Pakistan's services sector from 2010 to 2025. The research relies exclusively on secondary data collected from credible national and international sources, including the World Bank's World Development Indicators (WDI),

the Pakistan Bureau of Statistics (PBS), the State Bank of Pakistan (SBP), the Pakistan Telecommunication Authority (PTA), and the International Telecommunication Union (ITU). The use of annual data is particularly appropriate for analyzing long-term structural trends and macroeconomic relationships in the services sector, which has been the most dynamic and rapidly transforming segment of Pakistan's economy in recent years.

The study focuses on exploring both the short-run and long-run linkages between digitalization and sectoral economic growth. The dependent variable, economic growth, is measured through real GDP growth or services sector value added as a percentage of GDP. The independent variables representing digitalization include internet penetration, mobile cellular subscriptions, fixed broadband subscriptions, ICT exports, and the e-government development index. To control for macroeconomic influences, human capital, trade openness, and inflation are included as control variables. These variables were selected based on the theoretical framework and previous empirical studies emphasizing the role of information and communication technology, education, and openness in promoting economic development. The expected relationship between digitalization and economic growth is positive, as increased access to digital technologies tends to enhance productivity, efficiency, and innovation in the services sector.

The econometric model used in this study is the Autoregressive Distributed Lag (ARDL) bounds testing approach to co integration, developed by Pasaran, Shin, and Smith (2001). This method is chosen because it is suitable for small sample sizes and can handle a mixture of stationary I (0) and non-stationary I (1) variables. The ARDL model allows for simultaneous estimation of both long-run and short-run dynamics, making it ideal for capturing the temporal effects of digitalization on growth. In this framework, the long-run equation identifies equilibrium relationships among the variables, while the associated Error Correction Model (ECM) captures short-run adjustments toward that equilibrium. The ARDL specification will be used to test whether digitalization indicators such as

internet penetration and broadband subscriptions have significant long-run effects on Pakistan's services sector growth. Once long-run co integration is established through the bounds test, the ECM term will provide information on the speed of adjustment toward equilibrium when short-run deviations occur.

The empirical estimation will begin with descriptive and correlation analysis to summarize data patterns and identify potential multi collinearity. This will be followed by unit root testing using Augmented Dickey Fuller (ADF) and Phillips-Perron (PP) tests to determine the order of integration of each variable. After confirming stationarity properties, the ARDL bounds test for co integration will be performed to identify long-run associations. The long-run coefficients will then be estimated to measure the long-term impact of digitalization on economic growth, while the short-run dynamics will be examined through the ECM. Diagnostic tests, including the Breusch-Godfrey test for serial correlation, the Breusch-Pagan test for heteroscedasticity, and the Jarque Bera test for normality, will be applied to ensure model validity. Furthermore, the CUSUM and CUSUMSQ tests will be used to verify the structural stability of the model parameters over the sample period. Finally, the Granger causality test will be employed to examine the direction of causality between digitalization and economic growth.

The ARDL approach is particularly justified in this context because of its flexibility and efficiency in analyzing relationships among variables with different integration orders and its ability to work effectively with limited annual data. It also allows for the separation of long-term equilibrium relationships from short-term fluctuations, which is essential in understanding the dynamic impact of technological transformation on Pakistan's service-based economy. Since this study uses publicly available secondary data, there are no ethical concerns related to data collection; however, all data sources are acknowledged properly to ensure academic transparency and integrity. It is anticipated that the empirical results will reveal that digitalization measured through internet penetration, broadband use, ICT exports, and e-governance has a

significant and positive influence on the services sector's contribution to economic growth. These findings will not only validate the theoretical argument that digital transformation drives economic development but also provide valuable insights for policymakers in designing strategies to expand digital infrastructure, promote digital literacy, and enhance technology adoption in Pakistan's services industry.

3.2. Hypothesis Testing

Ho: There is no relation between economic growth in service and digitalization in Pakistan

H1: There is positive relation between economic and digitalization in Pakistan

3.3. Model Specification and Variables Description

To empirically assess the impact of digitalization on the economic growth of Pakistan's services sector, this study specifies an econometric model based on the neoclassical growth framework, extended to incorporate information and communication technology (ICT) indicators. The model assumes that digitalization acts as a productivity-enhancing factor that influences the performance of the services sector through innovation, connectivity, and efficiency gains. Following this theoretical foundation, the relationship between economic growth and digitalization can be expressed in a log-linear functional form as:

Model:

$$EG_t = \beta_0 + \beta_1 INP_t + \beta_2 MOB_t + \beta_3 FBB_t + \beta_4 EGD_t + \mu_t$$

Model Explanation:

Dependent Variable = Economic Growth.

The independent variables

- (1) Internet penetration,
- (2) Mobile cellular Subscription,
- (3) Fixed broadband subscription,
- (4) E-Governnance

Here EG_t denotes the Economic growth rate of the services sector in year t , measured by services sector value added as a percentage of GDP. The explanatory variables include

several indicators of digitalization and control variables that affect economic growth.

In this model, **economic growth (EG)** is the dependent variable, measured through the annual growth rate of the services sector or real GDP per capita. **Internet penetration (INT)** refers to the percentage of the population using the internet, representing the accessibility of digital networks. **Mobile cellular subscriptions (MOB)** denote the number of active mobile connections per 100 inhabitants, indicating digital connectivity. **Fixed broadband subscriptions (FBB)** capture the level of advanced internet infrastructure and data transmission capacity. **E-government development index (EGDI)** reflects the government's progress in providing online services and promoting digital governance.

Based on theoretical and empirical evidence, the expected signs of coefficients for all digitalization variables (INT, MOB, FBB, ICTE, EGDI) are positive, implying that greater digital adoption and higher educational investment enhance productivity and growth in the services sector. Trade openness may have an ambiguous effect depending on whether it promotes technology diffusion or exposes the sector to external shocks, while inflation is expected to have a negative impact on growth. The inclusion of these variables provides a comprehensive empirical framework to quantify how digital transformation contributes to Pakistan's service-sector expansion during the 2010–2025 period.

3.4. Data Analysis

The data analyzed through SPSS and MS Excel and run the model in context the multiple linear regression model. The data collected from different websites from 2010 to 2024. The GDP data measured in term of economic growth, and data collected from world bank group. The empirical analysis begins with a descriptive examination of the variables to summarize their characteristics and identify patterns over the 2010–2024 period. The data is the annual percentage of GDP of Pakistan (World Bank) The percentage of population using net in Pakistan, the data extract from the world bank indicator for all countries (World Bank Indicator). The data for our third

variables cellular mobile connection per one hundred inhabitants in Pakistan, got from ministry of information technology and telecommunication of Pakistan. For fixed broad band connection, the data gathered from the senses and economic information centers (CEICE). The E-Governance data collected for our independent variable for finding its effect on economic growth in Pakistan from service sector (Atiq et al., 2024). Summary statistics, including mean, median, standard deviation, and range, are computed for economic growth and digitalization indicators, while line graphs illustrate temporal trends in services sector growth, internet penetration, mobile subscriptions, broadband access, and e-government development.

Upon establishing integration, the long-run coefficients are estimated to quantify the impact of internet penetration, mobile subscriptions, broadband access, and e-government development on sectoral growth, while controlling for human capital, trade openness, and inflation. The short-run dynamics are analyzed through the associated Error Correction Model (ECM), where the error-correction term indicates the speed at which deviations from long-run equilibrium are corrected.

Chapter#4: Results and Conclusion

The results analyzed with SPSS and MS Excel for our model and demographic analysis. The

individual explanation of variables throughout fifteen years from 2010-2024. Explanation of the analyses diagram given below.

Graph: 4.1

The graph (4.1) depict the percentage of people with access to the internet has shown a consistent upward trend from 2010 to 2024. In the initial years from 2010 to 2014, the percentage started at around 8-10% and witnessed a gradual increase. As the years progressed from 2014 to 2020, the growth in internet access continued steadily, with the percentage rising from approximately 10% to

about 20%. The trend persisted with a moderate increase in internet access from 2020 to 2022. Notably, the period between 2022 to 2024 saw a sharp spike in the percentage of people gaining access to the internet, indicating a rapid expansion of internet penetration during these years.

Graph: 4.2

The graph (4.2) depicting Mobile Cellular Subscription trends from 2010 to 2024 reveals a notable pattern in the growth of mobile subscriptions. Initially, mobile cellular subscriptions exhibited an upward trend from 2010 leading up to 2013. However, a sharp decline in subscriptions was witnessed in 2013. Post-2013, the subscriptions resumed their growth trajectory, continuing to rise

steadily until approximately 2022. In the period from 2022 to 2024, the data indicates a stabilization or a slight decrease in mobile cellular subscriptions. This trend suggests fluctuations in mobile cellular subscription growth over the years, with a significant dip in 2013 followed by recovery and subsequent stabilization in recent years.

Graph: 4.3

The graph (4.3) illustrated Fixed Broadband Subscription trends from 2010 to 2024 reveals a distinct pattern in the adoption of fixed

broadband services. Initially, fixed broadband subscriptions remained minimal from 2010 to 2012. A notable spike in subscriptions was

observed in 2013, indicating a significant surge in fixed broadband uptake during that year. Following this peak, subscriptions experienced a sharp decline, reverting to levels comparable to those before the spike. Subsequently, from 2014 onwards, fixed broadband subscriptions

exhibited a gradual yet steady increase through to 2024. This trend suggests an initial anomaly in 2013 followed by a consistent growth pattern in fixed broadband subscriptions in the years thereafter.

Graph:4.4

The given (4.4) illustrate E-governance Development Index in Pakistan, as depicted in the diagram, illustrates the country's progress in adopting and developing e-governance from 2010 to 2024. The data reveals a trend of gradual improvement in e-governance development over the years.

Initially, from 2010 to around 2015, the index indicates a period of relative stability with minor fluctuations. Subsequently, from approximately 2016 to 2020, Pakistan

witnessed a gradual increase in the E-governance Development Index. A notable dip was observed in 2022, which was followed by a sharp increase in 2023 and a continued upward trajectory into 2024.

This pattern suggests that despite a brief setback in 2022, Pakistan's e-governance development has shown overall improvement, indicating efforts towards enhancing digital governance in the country.

Table 4.1
ANOVA

Model		Sum of Squares	df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
1	Regression	34.678	4	8.670	2.387	.121 ^b
	Residual	36.316	10	3.632		
Total		70.995	14			

a. **Dependent Variable:** Economic Growth

b. **Independent Variables:** (Constant), E governance Development Index, Mobil Cellular Subscription, INT PERCENTAGE OF PEOPLE ACCESS TO INTERNET, Fixed broad band subscription

The ANOVA table (4.1) summarizes the overall significance of your multiple linear regression model, where economic growth is the dependent variable, and digitalization indicators including E-Governance Development Index, Mobile Cellular Subscriptions, Internet Access (% of people using the internet), and Fixed Broadband Subscriptions are the independent variables.

1. Regression Sum of Squares, 34.678 The change in economic development explained by the four digitization indicators is It illustrates how much of the growth in the economy can be explained by digital aspects between 2010 and 2024.

2. Residual Sum of Squares (36.316) This is the unexplained change, the segment of economic expansion not covered by the model. It covers the consequences of other elements not accounted for in the study.

3. Sum of Squares total 70.995 The overall variation in economic development is this. It results from adding unexplained (residual) changes to explained (regression) variability.

4. F-statistic: 2.387 Taken together, the independent variables' capacity to significantly forecast economic expansion is tested by the F-value. In this instance, the F- value of 2.387 points to a modest impact of digitalisation on economic expansion.

5. Significance value (sig.= 0.121) Since the p-value of 0.121 exceeds the usual significance level of 0.05, the general regression model is not statistically significant. In other words, digitalization indicators taken together have no statistically significant influence on economic expansion throughout this era.

Although the regression model explains a reasonable part of the variation in economic growth (about 48.8%, calculated as $34.678 \div 70.995$), the model is not statistically significant ($p = 0.121 > 0.05$). This means that the combined effects of digitalization factors e-governance, internet access, mobile subscriptions, and broadband usage do not significantly explain changes in Pakistan's economic growth in the services sector between 2010 and 2024.

Although the regression model explains a good portion of the change in economic growth (about 48.8%, calculated as $34.678 \div 70.995$), the model is not Statistically relevant: $p = 0.121 > 0.05$.

This suggests that variations in Pakistan's economic performance are not significantly explained by the cumulative impact of digital components like e-governance, internet access, mobile subscriptions, and broadband usage. Between 2010 and 2024 in the services sector, growth in digitalizing. The ANOVA findings ($F = 2.387, p = 0.121$) imply that digitalization is beneficial but statistically insignificant influence on Pakistan's services industry economic expansion. While digital indicators account for almost half of the variance in development, their combined impact is not great enough to be deemed statistically significant. This means that although digitization helps with growth, other structural or economic elements may be more influential throughout the years 2010-2024.

Table 4.2
Coefficients^a

Model		Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized	t	Sig.
		B	Std. Error	Coefficients Beta		
1	(Constant)	2.431	10.388		.234	.820
	INT PERCENTAGE OF PEOPLE ACCESS TO INTERNET	.209	.127	.936	1.643	.131
	Mobie Cellular Subscription	.245	.162	1.065	1.512	.162
	Fixed broad band subscription	.041	.410	.103	.101	.922

E Development Index	governance	-56.109	20.538	-2.147	-2.732	.021
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a. Dependent Variable: Economic Growth
 a. Dependant Variable: Economic Growth

This table (4.2) offers results of several linear regression studies in which four indications of digitalisation are independent variables: Economic Growth is dependent variable.

1. Percentage of people with internet access
2. Subscription to Mobile Cellular Service
3. Broadband Subscriptions Set
4. Development Index for e-Governance

1. Constant (Sig. = 0.820, B = 2.431)

The constant reflects the projected economic growth's value when all digital indicators are zero.

Because significance value ($p = 0.820$) far exceeds 0.05, the constant is not statistically significant, therefore it offers no separate contribution to the model.

2. Access to the Internet (% of People Using the Internet)

Coefficient B = 0.209: unstandardized

A one-unit rise in internet access (i.e., a 1% increase in population using internet) is connected with an increase of 0.209 units in economic growth. maintaining other variables constant. Although the coefficient is positive, the p-value (0.131) exceeds 0.05, hence the impact is not statistically significant. $t = 1.643$; Sig. = 0.131;

Interpretation: In Pakistan's services industry, internet access has a small but favorable effect on economic expansion.

3. Cellular Subscription

Assuming all other variables remain constant, a one - unit increase in mobile subscriptions results in a 0.245- unit rise in economic growth .

B= 0.245.

• $t= 1.512$,Sig. 0.162

The positive coefficient indicates a favourable relationship , but the p value (0.162) suggest that this effect is statistically negligible .

Interpretation while the growth in mobile connection sustaines the economy , the impact is not great enough to be definitive.

4. Broadband Subscription Fixed

* Broadband subscription have a very modest positive influence on economic growth; $t = 0.101$, Sig = 0.922; the high p- value (0.922)

indicates that the link is statistically insignificant. Interpretation: Fixed broadband use in this model has little impact on growth, maybe as a result of low broadband penetration over the period.

5. Index of Development for E- Governance

• B = -56.109: keeping other factors constant, the negative coefficient shows that a one unit increase in the E-governance Index is related with a 56.109 unit reduction in economic growth.

* $t=-2.732$; Sig. = 0.021:

Because the p value is less than 0.05 this effect is statistically significant.

Interpretation: E- governance growth reveals a strong yet unfavourable link with economic expansion.

This could indicate that improvements in e-governance during 2010–2024 were followed by short-term adaptation expenses, inefficiencies, or structural changes that momentarily slowed expansion in services sector.

Overall Model Interpretation

• Only the E-Governance Development Index among the four digitization indicators shows a statistically significant impact on economic growth ($p = 0.021$).

• Its relationship is bad, though, therefore digital governance changes may not have yet resulted in observable economic advantages over the time span examined.

• Broadband connectivity, mobile subscriptions, and Internet access show positive but statistically insignificant impacts on growth.

Conclusion

Between 2010 and 2024, the regression results show that digital variables have varied impacts on Pakistan's economic growth in the services sector. While internet usage, Although their impacts are not statistically significant, mobile connection and broadband access support growth favorably. The E- Governance Development Index, on the other hand, has a significant but bad one. relationship with growth indicates governance digitalization could yet be in a transitory stage when changes have not yet shown in the form of real economic results. Generally, Pakistan's digital revolution promises long-term expansion according to the results, yet its near-term effects stay limited.

Policy Recommendations Based on Regression Results

1. Strengthen Implementation of E-Governance Reforms

1. Reinforcement of E-Governance Reform Implementation

The E-Governance Development Index indicated a substantial yet unfavorable effect on economic development. This implies Pakistan's digital governance initiatives might still not be effectively adopted or incorporated into public and service sectors even if they have been launched.

Suggestion on policy:

Among public officials, concentrate on digital literacy and capacity building.

Reduce complicated administrative digital processes to enable user-friendly e-governance systems.

- Make sure e-governance initiatives actually enhance service delivery and output rather than producing administrative slowdowns by means of frequent impact assessments.

2. Expand Affordable and rapid internet access.

There was a positive but not statistically significant link between economic expansion and internet use. This means that internet penetration helps the services industry but not yet enough or effectively to considerably increase it.

Suggesting policy:

Especially in rural and semi-urban locations, grow internet infrastructure spending.

Encourage public private collaborations to broaden broadband networks.

To improve digital inclusion, present subsidized data plans for startups, students, and small service companies.

2. Promote Mobile-Based Digital Entrepreneurship

Mobile cellular subscriptions also showed a positive but insignificant effect on growth. This indicates that while mobile usage is high, it is not being effectively leveraged for economic productivity.

Policy recommendation:

Encourage mobile banking, e-commerce, and app-based services that generate employment and innovation. Provide tax incentives and digital financing schemes for startups using mobile technology. Support the development of mobile skill training programs to turn mobile usage into an economic tool rather than just social communication.

3. Revitalize the Fixed Broadband Sector

Fixed broadband subscription had a **very weak and insignificant effect** on growth, possibly due to **low usage or outdated infrastructure**.

Policy recommendation:

- Modernize broadband infrastructure by promoting **fiber-optic connectivity** and **5G technology**.
- Lower installation costs for businesses and households.
- Encourage telecom companies to **bundle broadband services** with digital learning and remote work platforms to enhance productivity.

4. Integrate Digitalization into Service Sector Policy

The overall ANOVA result ($p = 0.121$) indicates that **digitalization collectively has a positive but not statistically significant effect** on economic growth. This means Pakistan's digital transformation is at an **early or uneven stage** across sectors.

Policy recommendation:

- Develop a **National Digitalization Strategy for the Services Sector**, aligning digital tools with trade, banking, education, and tourism.
- Foster **data-driven decision-making** in service industries to enhance efficiency.
- Promote **digital skills and innovation hubs** at universities and technical institutes to support human capital development.

Ensure Policy Continuity and Monitoring
Digital initiatives often fail to show quick results because of **policy discontinuity** or **weak monitoring**.

- **Policy recommendation:**

- Establish an **independent Digital Economy Council** to evaluate progress annually.
- Link government digital policies with measurable **economic performance indicators**.
- Encourage collaboration between ministries (IT, commerce, finance, education) to ensure digital policies reinforce one another.

Encourage Research and Data Transparency

The insignificant results may also reflect **data quality issues** or **incomplete digital measurement**.

- **Policy recommendation:**

- Improve **data collection and transparency** on digital indicators.
- Fund **academic and institutional research** to continuously assess the evolving link between digitalization and economic growth.

Conclusion

In the conclusion, the regression results highlight that Pakistan's digitalization efforts particularly in e-governance and ICT infrastructure are still developing. Policymakers should focus on improving the quality, accessibility, and integration of digital systems across the services sector. Strengthening governance implementation, expanding digital infrastructure, and enhancing human capital can turn

digitalization into a more effective driver of economic growth in the coming years.

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